

"ILHAQ" IS A FILM GLORIFYING HUMAN VALUES

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Abstract: this article presents the development processes of the film "Ilhak" and its analysis.

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The fire of war has dried up thousands of pillows in different parts of the human-inhabited earth. It is sad that wars are still going on in some countries. Children born when the war started are now growing up and shooting at each other in the battlefields. Many children spend the golden days of their childhood terrified by the rain of bullets, the roar of bombs, and the sound of rockets exploding. Millions of people separated from their homeland are facing the suffering of emigration. The historical-artistic film "Ilhaq" directed by Jahangir Akhmedov about one such terrible battle is very important in calling humanity to fight for peace.

The film "Ilhaq" is based on real events. The film tells about the life of Zulfiya Zakirova during the Second World War. Zulfiya sends all her sons to war, but they all die. Four of them had wives, and later they did not marry again. Although Zulfiya received black letters, until the last days of his life, he hopes for the return of his children. At the end of the film, it ends with the information about the graves of the war heroes who died in Russia and the image of these monuments.[1]

Before talking about this film, it is necessary to dwell on its title. In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" it is noted that the word

attachment is derived from the Arabic words "to wait", "to connect" and means to wait with hope. we can see that it is watered with the idea that it will never fade. The film covers love for the Motherland, mother, loyalty to the family, trust and patience, and gratitude. In particular, it started with the events of the construction of the "Big Fergana Canal" in 1939, but it mainly tells about the events that took place in Uzbekistan, which was considered the front line during the Second World War, which took place in 1941-1945 and killed more than twenty million people. While watching the film, we can see that the director has taken into account the real outcome of every event in it, and that this is based on the hard work of the filmmakers. In the first shots, the viewer gets acquainted with the unparalleled courage of our people in the construction of the canal, their faith in the future, and in the next shots, we watch with interest the life events related to the wedding ceremony in every Uzbek household.

As we mentioned above, the film begins with the description of the events of the construction of the "Big Fergana Canal" in 1939, which gained great socio-political and economic importance in the history of our country. It shows the channel construction process in very realistic episodes. While watching the film, it can be seen that the director has done a lot of preparation during the shooting process to ensure that this story comes out as it should. More than a thousand people dressed in period clothes and armed with the necessary equipment participate in the footage of the construction of the canal. These shots bring to life the real scene of the events of 1939 before the viewer's eyes. The fact that everyone involved in the construction is put in their place, the ability to focus the attention of the audience on the main character even in public scenes is undoubtedly a great achievement of the director. One of the most important factors in the successful release of the film is the fact that the filmmakers did not neglect every tool needed for these shots, including a hoe, spade, wheelbarrow, and stretchers. The same meticulousness and responsibility related to film scenery can be said in the example of Zulfia aya's house. Because in a historical film, such

decorations prepared in the process of filming are of great importance in ensuring the vitality of events. Director Jahangir Akhmedov said that the decoration of the courtyard of the house where Zulfiya Aya and her sons lived is almost no different from the reality. Analyzing the film "Ilhaq" from head to toe requires a lot of strength, strength and audience. The film uses a wide range of sources about the war. For example, from some of the works about the Second World War, namely, "Forty-five days" in the "Ufq" trilogy by Said Ahmed, "The construction process of the Great Fergana Canal", O'tkir Hashimov's frontline hardships in the novel "Between Two Doors", Saida's role as the chairman, Saida Zununova's "Conversation with the Spirit" Involuntarily, you will remember the thoughtful, mournful conversation of Zulfiya Aya with her late husband, played by Dilrom Karimova, the widow who married El in the epic. However, each frame of the film expresses its own sincerity, hard work and Uzbek tradition and spirit. That is, it is clearly felt that there is an elaborate artistic work at the base of the scenario, and that life events are coming to life. The words, dialogues, and events in the film are well structured. There are no excessive laughs, high-pitched talk, superficial similes. Although the events of the film begin with the public scenes of the construction of the Great Fergana Canal, it is mainly filled with episodes related to the family of Zulfiya Aya. At a time when the construction of the canal is in full swing, Zulfiya goes to the construction site in search of her son Muhammadjan, and the conversation between them captivates the audience with the true Uzbek spirit. It is through this image that the Mother figure is central in the film. Especially in this place, Shakir's song "Hola mounov is one more piece of bread" performed by If I get the young Mamajonov, will you spread it on the surbetkik?" He described each place in his own language and customs. In this case, the characters of the film are introduced one by one, and the first outlines of their lives and characters are given. The director skillfully used the art of contrast in the first scenes of the film. For example, while depicting the scene of happiness and harmony in bright colors, he emphasized the harmonious life, the beautiful scenery

of the singing scene, the episodes of one of the film's characters having a child after a few years, and the youngest child entering school, especially the wedding ceremony. In front of the viewer's eyes, it is as if such happy-blissful days are eternal and flawless. However, this one news about the beginning of the war takes away all joy, joy and happiness from everyone's heart. The director pays attention to every small detail here. One of them is the crushing of the straw house made by the children on the roadside by the wheels of the car, which is a sign of the destructive force of the so-called war. This episode is seen as an allusion to the disappearance of the men of an entire family due to war, the separation of mothers from their children, brides from their spouses, and children from their fathers. This news turns people's high spirits into sadness. In the film, this situation is also depicted as a very vivid scene. We can see how the news about the war affected the psyche of people by their involuntary stiffness and not even touching the delicacies on the table. In general, such symbolic image processes are prominent in the film, showing that the historical environment is vividly depicted. The hard and difficult days that began when the mobilization for the war was announced played an important role in illuminating the characters of the film's heroes one after another. Someone hung the morsel in his mouth, while someone else could not withstand the tests and took the path of betrayal. At this time, the drama of the film became more and more tense. It can be noticed that special attention was paid to ensuring the originality of the characters of the film during the shooting process. In this place, the director paid attention to the uniqueness of each character's speech, and made good use of each speech process. Examples of this are the words of Akhmadjan performed by Iskandar Elmurodov: "Let's see how the crows fly", Yusufjan's "One kiss" performed by Bunyod Rahmatullaev, Yusufjan's speech on behalf of his father: "Don't cry, I'll bring you a double-breasted vest from Leningrad". It is worth noting that such words and thoughts that sound from the language of the characters are repeated again and again in various processes of their fates, and every time they are returned, they indicate a special spirit, meaning,

essence, and a special tragedy. This is also one of the skills of the director, according to the famous film director Felli, "The director is Columbus on the ship. He wants to explore America, and the crew wants to go home." How to keep sailors interested?[2]

It's a lot of work. Indeed, during the filming of this "Ilhaq" movie, Jahangir Akhmedov behaved like Colum on the ship and skillfully demonstrated his work efficiency. This is reflected in the way the actors play their characters in a natural, real-life way. At this point, it is worth mentioning that Rahmatulla Kurbanov, who played the character of the deaf-mute Chori in the film, was able to portray his character convincingly. All his actions are believably realistic. In the film, this image brought some impressive, thoughtful audience. This is also a discovery and achievement of the director. We listened to the director's thoughts about this: "It has been more than 10 years since the idea of this film was born and formed as a script. I was born and raised in the village of Khanabad, Zangiota district, Tashkent region, that is, in the village where Zulfia Aya lived. I grew up in the neighborhood named after Zulfiya Zakirova and studied at the school of the same name. My first teacher is aya's granddaughter-in-law. Through the stories I heard from their children, I was very impressed by the aya's tenacity. I want to say that the script of this film was formed from my childhood. The film's working title was Black Letter, later renamed Mother of the Five Warriors. After our President spoke about Zulfia Aya's tenacity on May 9 - Day of Remembrance and Appreciation, I decided to make a film of the script in my hand, and the final title was "Ilhaq". In order for the audience to understand what the horror of the war took away from people's lives, we started the film with the image of the happy days of the mother, full of happiness and joy of her children. [3]

In the successful release of the film, the fact that the chosen topic is not a fabric, that is, it has a real-life basis, was of great importance. At the core of the events reflected in it, we can see the interpretation of the events described in Alinazar Egamnazarov's essay "Mother of Five Warriors". Each of the main

characters in the film, Zulfia Zakirova and her children Mamajon, Isaqjon, Ahmadjon, Wahabjon and Yusufjon, who did not return from the Second World War, and her four daughters-in-law, who took on the hard work behind the front, are real historical figures. The director tries to reflect the conflicting real life of the people of that time in each episode. Especially in the person of the chairman, this person who "does not get tired" of repeatedly explaining his duty to Stalin tries to turn a blind eye to it in the example of his family. "Even Yusuf is going to war. Why don't you let me go, father!" The conflict between the two forces in the society can be seen in episodes such as when he scolded his son who protested, and promised not only to take him out of the war, but also to use his position and position to marry a girl who was Yusuf's lover. In the film "Ilhaq", the mother's sincere hope for her children was revealed at the end of the film. That is, at the end of the war, Zulfiya's youngest son attached a message that did not come, and even the funeral was not read for the older children, until 1961, when his grandson went to Leningrad and found his uncle's grave and brought a handful of grave soil from there. "Your Yusufjo has arrived. "Duhoba brought you a vest from Leningrad," he said, throwing it into the mother's hands from the soil of her child's grave. The mother said, "Now the funeral can be held for my children, as well as mine. "It's no wonder that every viewer who saw this image had tears in their eyes.

Of course, it is impossible to express all opinions about the movie "Ilhaq" in one article. In order to do this, we think that it is necessary to write a very large treatise about the film, to analyze the events depicted in it from thread to needle, and to shed light on the high human qualities that made Zulfia Zakirova's fate the symbol of a strong and courageous Uzbek woman. We found it necessary to conclude our words with the following comments made by the actress Dilorom Karimova, who embodied the image of the mother, at one of the events organized after the screening of the film, regarding the sad fate of Zulfia Aya: "The world is built on the wisdom of each person's life." Did Ayamiz know that such days would come? They lived in extreme pain and suffering. They left with the pain of losing

their five children. The other side of the scale is the wisdom of today. This film made the name of Zulfiya aya famous all over the world!"

Used literature

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